

Fluoremetric Determination of Pyrimethamine in Pharmaceutical Preparations

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A simple and sensitive fluoremetric procedure is described for the analysis of pyrimethamine in dosage forms. The substance can be determined in pharmaceutical preparations by its strong fluorescence in 1N H₂SO₄ ($\lambda_{excitation} = 321$ nm, $\lambda_{emission} = 425$ nm) with a detection limit of 1 ng μ l⁻¹. The addition of molecules of sulphadoxine causes a quenching in the region of excitation and emission of the former compound

THE continued use of Daraprim, Fansidar and Maloprim as antimalarials^{1,2} stimulated our interest in the evaluation of a selective and sensitive method for the detection and determination of the constituents in tablet and syrup preparations. While Daraprim contains mainly pyrimethamine (2,4-diamino-5-*p*-chlorophenyl-6-ethyl pyrimidine), Fansidar and Maloprim are unique preparations containing pyrimethamine in combination with sulphadoxine [4-(4-aminobenzene-sulphonamide)-5,6-dimethoxy pyrimidine] and dapsone (4,4-diaminodiphenylsulphone), respectively.

In our earlier work on Fansidar, we devised a gravimetric and uv method for the simultaneous determination of its constituents^{3,4}. Further, our preliminary experiments had shown that one of the constituents had a strong fluorescence under uv light of wavelength 254/366 nm. The present work was undertaken as followup to develop a fluoremetric procedure for the analysis of pyrimethamine because to date no such method has been reported for its analysis.

Experimental

The fluorescence spectra were taken on a Perkin-Elmer LS-5 luminescence spectrophotometer, consisting of an integral 83 W xenon lamp as light source, excitation monochromator (230-720 nm) and emission monochromator (250-800 nm). The size of the glass cell used was 10 nm. The photometer was operated at full sensitivity.

The pharmaceutical grade pyrimethamine, sulphadoxine and dapsone were employed as standards. The commercial preparations analysed were Fansidar tablets, Fansidar syrup and Daraprim tablets. Diacetyl pyrimethamine was synthesised following the reported procedure⁵. All reagents and chemicals used were of analytical grade (B.D.H., England).

Solutions: The solutions for analysis of each drug were prepared by dilution of stock solution of the individual drugs which had been prepared in 1 N H₂SO₄. Sulphuric acid solutions were prepared by dilutions with distilled water.

Calibration curve: The method adopted was based on the standard procedure⁶⁻⁸. A stock solution of pure pyrimethamine powder was prepared in 1 N H₂SO₄. Appropriate dilutions of the stock solution were made to give concentrations 10, 20, 30, 35 and 40 μ g ml⁻¹. The solutions were transferred to a 10 nm glass cell and the fluorescence intensities measured at room temperature for each solution (Table 1). The background intensity due to H₂SO₄ was also determined.

TABLE 1—FLUORESCENCE FOR PYRIMETHAMINE IN 1 N H₂SO₄

Sl. no	Concn. μ g ml ⁻¹	Fluorescence intensity
1.	40	305.4
2.	35	275.2
3.	30	247.0
4.	20	195.8
5.	10	177.7

Extraction and analysis of Daraprim tablets
The procedure used was similar to those described in literature⁷⁻⁹. Twenty tablets were weighed accurately and the average tablet weight was calculated. The samples were ground to fine powder and a quantity corresponding to the average tablet weight was transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask. The powder was dissolved in 1 N H₂SO₄ and the solution filtered to obtain a clear solution. The filtrate was diluted with 1 N H₂SO₄ to bring the concentration to 10 μ g ml⁻¹. The fluorescence

intensity of the acid solution was measured in the same manner as for the standard solution.

Chromatographic separation of Fansidar tablets and analysis: Twenty tablets were accurately weighed and the average tablet weight was determined. Five tablets (3.446 g) were ground to a fine powder and transferred to the top of a glass column (50 cm × 2 cm dia) previously packed with 110 g of neutral activated alumina (110 g; activity 1). The column was eluted with a mixture of diethyl ether and chloroform (750 ml, 1 : 9) and fractions of 25 ml were collected. The fractions were monitored on silica gel tlc plates and their R_f values determined. The fractions were allowed to air-dry and their m.p.s. recorded. The tlc plates and the dried residues were studied under uv of wavelength 254/366 nm for the presence of blue fluorescence. Pyrimethamine which eluted first was completely removed. The column was thereafter eluted with methanol (600 ml) and 100 ml fractions of elutes collected. The fractions were combined and concentrated under reduced pressure.

The dried residues of pyrimethamine were combined and weight equivalent to 25 mg of labelled content of drug was dissolved in 1 N H₂SO₄. On further dilution of the stock solution, different concentrations were prepared and their fluorescence determined.

Extraction of Fansidar syrups: The method comprised to pouring Fansidar syrup (15 ml) into a separating funnel, followed by a mixture (30 ml) of diethyl ether and acetone in equal volumes. The mixture was vigorously shaken and allowed to stand after which the lower layer containing the drug compounds was preserved. Similarly, four extractions were performed for each of the 15 ml sample preparations. The extracts were combined and washed with H₂O and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. The drying agent was removed by filtration and the solvent containing the product was removed under reduced pressure to obtain a fine powder of drug mixture. The powder was dried at 105° and treated in the same manner as in the case of Fansidar tablets.

Analysis with sulphadoxine and quenching of fluorescence: A solution containing a concentration of 100 ng μl^{-1} of pure pyrimethamine was prepared in 1 N H₂SO₄ and its fluorescence intensity measured. To this solution was added pure sulphadoxine in the concentrations of 100 and 200 ng μl^{-1} in 1 N H₂SO₄, respectively, and the fluorescence measurements were again made for the solutions.

Analysis with Dapsone: Solutions containing concentration of 40 and 35 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of pure pyrimethamine powder were prepared in 1 N H₂SO₄

and their fluorescence intensities were measured. To the solutions were added pure dapsone in the concentrations 200 and 800 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, respectively, in 1 N H₂SO₄, respectively, and fluorescence was again measured for these solutions.

Analysis with diacetylpyrimethamine: Diacetylpyrimethamine, a possible methabolite of pyrimethamine, was prepared according to the known procedure⁵. Solutions in the concentration of 200 and 800 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ were prepared in 1 N H₂SO₄ and added to the solutions of 40 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of pyrimethamine, and fluorescence was determined for these solutions

Results and Discussion

This study shows that analysis of constituents of Fansidar can not be achieved simultaneously by fluoremetric procedure because of the fact that sulphadoxine does not possess any native fluorescence and a causes a quenching in the fluorescence produced by pyrimethamine solutions. This effect of quenching is shown in the Fig 1.

Fig. 1. Quenching effect produced by sulphadoxine; 15 cm – 100 ng μl^{-1} pyrimethamine only, 7 cm – 100 ng μl^{-1} pyrimethamine and 100 ng μl^{-1} sulphadoxine, 3.25 cm – 100 ng μl^{-1} pyrimethamine and 200 ng μl^{-1} sulphadoxine.

It should also be pointed out that the separation of the constituents of Fansidar by column chromatography is time-consuming and cumbersome. Advantage was taken of the solubility difference between pyrimethamine and sulphadoxine, the latter being insoluble in ether chloroform. The constituents were identified by their known m p and R_f values.

In the case of Daraprim, fluoremetric procedure becomes the most selective, sensitive and precise method of determination for the first time in this study. The fluorescence produced is strong and

Fig. 2. Excitation spectra : emission, 321 nm ; scan speed, 60 nm min⁻¹ ; excitation slit, 2.5 nm ; emission slit, 2.5 nm ; concn. of pyrimethamine, 40 μg ml⁻¹.

the intensity remains unchanged for at least 24 h. The excitation and emission spectra are shown in the Figs. 2 and 3, respectively. The limit of detection for pyrimethamine is 1 ng μl⁻¹. The excitation

Fig. 3. Emission spectra : excitation, 425 nm ; scan speed, 240 nm min⁻¹ ; excitation slit, 10 nm ; emission slit, 10 nm ; concn. of pyrimethamine, 40 μg ml⁻¹.

spectrum shows a fluorescence at a wavelength 425 nm and the emission spectrum shows a fluorescence at a wavelength 321 nm.

When fluorescence measurements for pyrimethamine were determined in the presence of Dapsone, it was found that intensity of fluorescence for pyrimethamine remained unchanged and no quenching took place. Thus pyrimethamine can be determined by fluoremetry in the presence of Dapsone without any interference from the latter.

Diacetylpyrimethamine, which is a possible metabolite of pyrimethamine does not possess any fluorescence, and when it was added to the solutions of pyrimethamine, it did not alter the intensity of fluorescence for pyrimethamine and cause any interference. Further, the effect of variation of pH that maximum emission for pyrimethamine occurs at lower pH (1-2) while it decreases at higher pH levels.

The fluorescence measurements were made at laboratory temperature, and on heating the solutions of pyrimethamine there was no marked change in the fluorescence intensity.

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